

WAVELET METHODOLOGY OF MARKET ANALYSIS AS A COMPONENT OF DECISION
MAKING IN THE CONDITIONS OF FORMATION DIGITAL ECONOMY

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ABSTRACT

Modern transformation of business is influenced by the widespread introduction of Internet technologies, computer equipment and methods of digital processing and transmission of data. These tools for changing the conditions of business cover all stages and areas. The key direction of such transformation is the validity of the decisions taken, where a comprehensive market analysis should be taken into account. Such analysis includes both the validity of attracting various necessary resources and the exit with finished products. For such analysis, it is possible to use various market indicators, among which market indices are highlighted in this work. Based on this, the article considers the dynamics of individual world market indices and their relationship. Such analysis allows you to justify the time to enter the market for the implementation of various business strategies. For the purposes of such analysis, the wavelet coherence method is used. The work presents graphs and diagrams that allow you to evaluate the effectiveness of the presented course of research, the effectiveness of the results obtained. The results obtained will be useful for substantiating strategies for entering the market in the context of the formation of a market economy.

Keywords: Analysis, Market, Methodology, Decision Making, Wavelet Coherence, Time Series, Digital Economy.

Introduction

Modern business conditions imply the wide use of various tools necessary for objective analysis and secure transfer of available information. Such tools are primarily based on Internet technologies, the use of computer technology, digital methods and approaches in data research. All this is generalized through the formation of the so-called digital economy [1]-[3]. The key feature of such an economy is: handling digital data, their appropriate storage and transfer between various interested parties of economic relations. In general, this allows for effective business management, the development of individual business entities, and the achievement of economic balance and stability.

The digital economy is of particular importance in making balanced and objective decisions based on formalization and generalization using modern analytical tools. In this case, various methods and approaches can be used, both classical [4]-[18] and special ones, allowing to consider hidden negative trends and ways to overcome them [19]-[27]. The integrated use of such tools contributes to making more effective decisions, which are also aimed at developing the digital economy.

Among the individual methods and approaches, it is necessary to highlight those based on the wavelet methodology and allowing to evaluate the corresponding economic dynamics for making the necessary decisions [28]-[39]. The wavelet methodology allows considering the dynamics of various data in their interrelation and at different time intervals. This allows forming a certain strategy in decision-making.

Among the areas of development of the digital economy, from the point of view of making informed decisions, it is necessary to highlight the market analysis, which is important for doing business and its development. In this case, various market segments can be considered. For such analysis, quotes for various securities are distinguished among the sources of information [28]-[30], [32], [33]. The analysis of such quotes allows, as to determine the time of entering the relevant

market segment, and the time of replenishment with the necessary resources or placement of finished products on the market.

Thus, the main objective of this paper is to consider the use of wavelet methodology for decision-making when analyzing a certain market segment in the context of the formation of a digital economy. For these purposes, a brief analysis of related studies is carried out; the choice of a separate market segment is justified for considering the possibilities of using wavelet methodology and conducting the corresponding analysis.

Related work

Given the subject matter of this chosen research area, it is worth noting the many relevant scientific papers. Some of these scientific papers are devoted to the theoretical aspects of the research, others to the practical ones. Based on this, a brief analysis of some of the papers is presented below.

The study by L. H. Melnyk, O. I. Karintseva, O. V. Kubatko, Y. M. Derevianko and O. M. Matsenko examines the issues of restructuring socio-economic systems as a component of the formation of the digital economy [40]. The authors emphasize that in order to fulfill the tasks of its existence, any system must perform a set of interconnected functions. Therefore, it is important in the context of economic transformation that such functions are not lost. Based on this, the paper proposes a scheme for such a transformation and characterizes individual types of restructuring of socio-economic systems in modern digital transformations [40]. At the same time, it is also shown that the structure of economic systems is the most important subject of managing socio-economic development, and the analysis of restructuring processes is an effective tool for substantiating management decisions [40]. This confirms the importance of considering the stated goal of the study in our work.

C. Ding, C. Liu, C. Zheng and F. Li study technological innovation and high-quality economic development as the foundation of the digital economy [41]. The authors also discuss the impact of the digital economy on high-quality economic development using China as an example. For this purpose, the mechanism and effect of regional heterogeneity in the impact of the digital economy on the level of high-quality economic development in 30 Chinese provinces from 2011 to 2019 were investigated [41]. It is shown that the digital economy can promote a high level of economic development. It is also noted that technological innovation is a key link in transferring the digital economy to high-quality development [41].

D. Ma and Q. Zhu analyze the dynamics of innovation as a driving force for the development of the digital economy [42]. In particular, the paper examines the level of urban digital economy and high-quality green development in China. The authors notes that the digital economy can directly stimulate high-quality green development [42]. The paper also notes that the obtained results can provide decision-making recommendations for policymakers and experts in emerging economies to improve green development. However, to make effective decisions, it is necessary to use modern market analysis tools, which emphasizes the importance of the chosen research objective in our work.

In the study by X. Zhu and K. Liu, a systematic review and future directions of the digital economy are conducted [43]. Particular attention is paid to sharing. Based on this, the paper considers the product life cycle assessment technology as one of the advanced and key technologies in the field of green design and green manufacturing [43]. It also notes the importance of choosing an analysis method for making appropriate management decisions.

L. Wang and J. Shao study the relationship between entrepreneurship and energy efficiency in the context of digital economy development [44]. The authors note that entrepreneurship, as an endogenous force driving economic growth, has an important impact on the development of the digital economy. Based on this, the work notes that the digital economy significantly increases energy efficiency. At the same time, with the increase in the level of economic development, the role of the digital economy in promoting energy efficiency gradually increases [44]. Thus, the

digital economy plays a decisive role in promoting energy efficiency and economic development in general.

A. Musaev, A. Makshanov and D. Grigoriev conduct a statistical analysis of current quotes of financial instruments in conditions of market chaos [45]. The article examines various approaches to the construction of regression computational schemes using quotes of financial instruments as regressors [45]. At the same time, the authors note that violation of the requirements of repeatability of the experiment complicates the use of the traditional approach to averaging data. Therefore, such studies are becoming the main method for studying the effectiveness of forecasting algorithms and analyzing observation series [45]. Nevertheless, this allows us to build quite effective rational strategies for managing trading operations.

X. Yang, Y. Zhang and M. Wei investigate a three-stage method for analyzing market concentration and its efficiency using the example of the functioning of airports in the Yangtze River Delta [46]. For these purposes, the authors propose a method that combines analytical methodologies and data envelopment analysis (DEA) to analyze the changing trend and correlation of passenger transportation market concentration [46]. The work also uses such data evaluation methods as the Hirschman-Hoefenthal index, the Gini index and the analysis of pure shift effects, as well as the super efficiency method to study the correlation of pure shift with airport performance [46]. Such analysis allows for the assessment of the activities of both individual market structures and their groups.

The study [47] examines the features of using dynamic Fourier methods and wavelets for analyzing stock market data, in particular, for estimating the power spectrum of returns. At the same time, the narrowing process with the DFT technique and the scaling function with the wavelet methodology are used to estimate the power spectrum [47]. This allows avoiding spectral leakage or a break in the sequence. The authors note that the power spectrum is effective for characterizing minute and per-minute data corresponding to different frequencies [47]. Thus, the paper considers an approach that allows for the effective use of all variables of stationary time series for analysis. This emphasizes the importance of using the wavelet methodology to conduct the corresponding analysis.

O. K. Diallo, P. Mendy and A. Burlea-Schiopoiu use wavelet analysis to assess market efficiency based on the sector indices of the WAEMU stock exchange [48]. For this purpose, the market structure is considered and the generalized Hurst index is calculated using the discrete wavelet transform (DWT) and wavelet leader transform (WLT) approaches. The data used are daily data on its seven sector indices from December 31, 2013 to January 4, 2019 of the WAEMU stock exchange [48]. It is noted that the dynamics of the indices reveals the characteristics of short memory or, in some cases, long memory. This emphasizes the importance of using wavelet analysis methods.

Thus, market analysis is one of the key areas for achieving the goals of digital economy development. At the same time, various methods and approaches can be used to conduct such analysis. Among such methods, approaches based on the wavelet analysis methodology should be highlighted. At the same time, to summarize the results of the study, the dynamics of individual world market indices is considered.

Wavelet coherence as an analysis tool

The methodology of wavelets is chosen as a basis for conducting the corresponding market analysis, where the assessment of wavelet coherence is distinguished. Such an assessment is applied to data that are presented in the form of time series. The assessment of wavelet coherence has found wide application in the study of similar data [28]-[37].

Such an assessment allows us to consider significant relationships between data, both on the entire research interval and on its individual intervals. At the same time, the depth of the corresponding connections is also studied. This is important for developing market entry strategies,

investment strategies, and the development of the digital economy. The following formalization is used for such analysis [49], [50]:

$$R^2(a, h) = \frac{|\Omega(a^{-1}W_{k(t)d(t)}(a, h))|^2}{\Omega(a^{-1}|W_{k(t)}(a, h)|^2)\Omega(a^{-1}|W_{d(t)}(a, h)|^2)}, \quad (1)$$

where:

$W(a, h)$ – values of transverse wavelet spectra,

a, h – the scale and center of time localization that determine the scale of the wavelet transform,

$k(t), d(t)$ – series of data that we study over time t ,

Ω – smoothing operator,

$R^2(a, h)$ – square of the wavelet coherence coefficient. $0 \leq R^2(a, h) \leq 1$. If these values tend to zero, then we have a weak correlation. Otherwise we have a strong correlation [49].

Dynamics of individual world market indices as an object of research

To conduct the corresponding analysis, we will consider the quotes of individual world market indices. Among such indices are: Nikkei 225 (N225), FTSE 100 (FTSE), Dow Jones Industrial Average (DJI) and S&P/ASX 200 (AXJO). The choice of such data is due to the fact that the presented indices reflect the activities of various market segments, business entities and take into account various regional features of the world stock market. Thus, the Nikkei 225 (N225) index is listed on the Japanese stock exchange, FTSE 100 (FTSE) – the United Kingdom, Dow Jones Industrial Average (DJI) – the United Kingdom and S&P/ASX 200 (AXJO) – Australia. All data represent the dynamics of the corresponding quotes in the period from January 2022 to February 2025 (from the website <https://investing.com/>).

Fig. 1 shows the dynamics of the Nikkei 225 (N225) and FTSE 100 (FTSE) indexes.

Figure 1: Dynamics of the Nikkei 225 (N225) and FTSE 100 (FTSE) indexes

In general, the dynamics of the Nikkei 225 (N225) and FTSE 100 (FTSE) indices are different, which is natural, since they reflect quotes for shares of different companies. In addition, it is necessary to take into account the specifics of the functioning of each exchange where such indices are quoted.

In particular, the dynamics of the Nikkei 225 (N225) index in the first third of the period under study is significantly variable. Then, a rapid growth of the index is observed and in the last third, some stabilization of the dynamics of this index is observed.

For the dynamics of the FTSE 100 index (FTSE), a less dynamic growth is observed. In most of this dynamics, one can see the so-called variable stability of the dynamics under study.

It should be emphasized that the dynamics of the Nikkei 225 (N225) and FTSE 100 (FTSE) are generally increasing over the time interval under study.

Fig. 2 shows the dynamics of the Dow Jones Industrial Average (DJI) and S&P/ASX 200 (AXJO) indexes.

a) Dow Jones Industrial Average (DJI)

b) S&P/ASX 200 (AXJO)

Figure 2: Dynamics of the Dow Jones Industrial Average (DJI) and S&P/ASX 200 (AXJO) indexes

The dynamics of the Dow Jones Industrial Average (DJI) and S&P/ASX 200 (AXJO) indices differ from each other and from the dynamics of the Nikkei 225 (N225) and FTSE 100 (FTSE) indices. At the same time, it should be noted that on certain time intervals, the dynamics of the Dow Jones Industrial Average (DJI) and S&P/ASX 200 (AXJO) indices are generally similar.

However, upon closer examination, such similarity differs in detail. Therefore, for a more detailed analysis, it is advisable to conduct an additional analysis of such dynamics using the wavelet coherence methodology. This is especially important in the context of the formation and development of the digital economy, when it is important to know the feasibility of entering a certain market segment, the time of such an exit.

Comparative assessment of the mutual dynamics of the studied data

To further investigate, let us consider some estimates of wavelet coherence (Fig. 3 and Fig. 4) between the data series presented above (Fig. 1 and Fig. 2).

a) N225 & FTSE

b) DJI & AXJO

Figure 3: Wavelet coherence estimates between N225 & FTSE and DJI & AXJO respectively

Fig. 3 shows the estimates of wavelet coherence between N225 & FTSE (Fig. 3a) and DJI & AXJO (Fig. 3b), respectively.

Based on the data in Fig. 3a, we should talk about the fragmentation of the estimates of wavelet coherence between the dynamics of such indices as N225 & FTSE. Moreover, such

fragmentation is characteristic both from the point of view of the time axis and the depth of the emerging relationships. This allows us to select the most effective time periods for entering the relevant market segments.

Based on the data in Fig. 3b, it is also worth noting some fragmentation between the dynamics of the DJI & AXJO indices. However, with the growth of the depth of the relationships, such fragmentation flows into a constant and significant dependence between the considered data series. This allows making long-term forecasts, which is important in the context of the development of the digital economy.

Fig. 4 shows the wavelet coherence estimates between N225 & DJI (Fig. 4a) and FTSE & AXJO (Fig. 4b), respectively.

Figure 4: Wavelet coherence estimates between N225 & DJI and FTSE & AXJO respectively

The data in Fig. 4 also demonstrate fragmentation in the estimates of wavelet coherence between the dynamics of the N225 & DJI and FTSE & AXJO index values. However, the fragmentation of the estimates between the dynamics of the FTSE & AXJO index values is much denser than for the dynamics of the index values between N225 & DJI. At the same time, with an increase in the depth of the relationship, the density of fragmentation between the dynamics of the FTSE & AXJO index values increases.

In general, it should be emphasized that the use of wavelet coherence for market analysis in the context of the development of the digital economy is appropriate and necessary. This is based on the fact that wavelet coherence estimates expand the implementation of the corresponding analysis and allow us to justify various strategies for entering the market.

Conclusion

The article substantiates the concept of the feasibility and necessity of using wavelet methodology for market analysis when making decisions in the context of the formation and development of the digital economy. For these purposes, among possible approaches to wavelet analysis, a method for obtaining wavelet coherence estimates is considered. The dynamics of individual world indices as sources for obtaining the necessary information for decision-making are also considered. This justification is also based on the analysis of existing studies on the selected topic.

Based on the dynamics of individual world indices, the corresponding wavelet coherence estimates are considered, which allow for a better understanding of the functioning of individual market segments and their interrelationships. The expediency of using wavelet coherence estimates for conducting the corresponding analysis is shown. It is noted that the obtained results can be used for decision-making in the context of the formation of the digital economy. This is possible based on a detailed analysis of the interrelations between individual market segments.

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